

Do we need to agree on what resilience is? A proposed practical and participatory approach

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Abstract

Resilience is a term frequently used nowadays in different contexts, including transportation. However, definitions vary even within sectors. Communities play also a vital role in decision-making that relates to transportation and/or to its infrastructure. This paper presents different views on 'resilience', and 'community resilience' and a practical and participatory methodology on how to build 'community resilience' that may support the development of technologies and/or decisions in transportation. Although the proposed approach was implemented in the context of the Horizon 2020 EU-funded project 'Search and Rescue' which concerns disaster management, several of the involved stakeholders constitute also stakeholders in the transportation sector. The pros and cons and thoughts for further improvement or adaptation of the proposed approach are also discussed.

Keywords: Resilience, Community Resilience, Disaster Preparedness, Crisis Management.

1. Introduction

The motivation for this work stemmed from the existing diversion and variability of definitions for 'resilience' that may be encountered in the scientific literature and the relevant, and often different, perception of the term between stakeholders, experts and practitioners in transportation and disaster management, to mention only a few. When the aforementioned complexities are combined with different notions and definitions related to the use of the terms 'community' and 'community resilience', the challenge to achieve a common understanding and reliable communication between involved parties in research projects and/or on the field applications escalates even further.

Such was the case in the context of the (ongoing) EU-funded research and innovation project H2020 'Search and Rescue' (S&R - www.search-and-rescue.eu) where gaps for 'community resilience' had to be analyzed so as to provide recommendations for the development of wearables/technologies and their operationalization during S&R pilots. 'Communities play also an important role in transportation and hence the need to consider these within the context of 'resilience'.

As much as the aforementioned terms were easily understood by everyone, it was clear that perceptions differed substantially on all of these.

Hence, the objectives of this paper are to:

- Introduce the reader to representative definitions and major schools of thought in relation to ‘resilience’ by also highlighting the complexity that may rise when combining this term with ‘community’ to refer to ‘community resilience’.
- Provide food for thought and stimulate discussion in the scientific community with regard to the need to agree on a common definition for resilience.
- Propose and discuss a participatory approach, which could be adapted in different settings and contexts, to help bridging the identified perception gaps in order to improve communication and allow for positive synergies among collaborating parties.
- Synthesize the above with key user needs in order to integrate elements of ‘resilience’ into the development of technologies and /or their operationalization. In this context, we should clarify that the aim of the proposed approach is not at this point of development to provide a concrete measure of ‘resilience’ or of ‘community resilience’ which is in itself a whole different topic for debate and further research.

To achieve these goals, the rest of the paper is organized as follows: in section 2 a representative review of the literature on ‘resilience’, and ‘community resilience’ is provided. In section 3, the proposed approach in terms of methodology and methods is presented. Section 4 includes a discussion on potential application of the proposed approach, its strengths and potential shortcomings. Conclusions and possible research directions are presented in section 5.

2. Literature review

‘Resilience’ has recently become the new “hot” word in the scientific community that accompanies all sort of calls for proposals, actions and formulation of framework. Everyone sets a precondition for ‘resilience’ in their respective vision. However, the notion of ‘resilience’ has evolved over the years and it is evident that this notion is not perceived in a uniform or similar way across the different actors. This evidence applies to all sources that attempt to define the term, irrespectively of whether these are scientific publications, national/international organizations, technical reports or other. **Table 1** provides representative examples.

Table 1: Representative definitions for ‘resilience’

Resilience definitions	Type of Source
<i>The essence of sustainability. The ability to resist disorder.</i>	Scientific paper (Fiksel, 2003)
<i>Capability of a system to maintain its functions and structure in the face of internal and external change and to degrade gracefully when it must.</i>	Scientific paper (Alenby & Fink, 2005)
<i>The ability of a system, community or society exposed to hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate to and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner,</i>	International Organization

<i>including through the preservation and restoration of its essential basic structures and functions.</i>	(UNISDR, 2009)
<i>A capability to anticipate, prepare for, respond to, and recover from threats w/ minimum damage to social well-being, the economy and the environment.</i>	World Road Association (PIARC, 2015)
<i>The ability of individuals, communities, organizations or countries exposed to disasters, crises and underlying vulnerabilities to anticipate, prepare for, reduce the impact of, cope with and recover from the effects of shocks and stresses without compromising their long-term prospects.</i>	(IFRC - International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, 2016)
<i>The ability of a system, community or society exposed to hazards to resist, absorb, accommodate, adapt to, transform and recover from the effects of a hazard in a timely and efficient manner, including through the preservation and restoration of its essential basic structures and functions through risk management.</i>	International Organization (UNDRR - United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, 2017)
<i>The ability to prepare and plan for, absorb, recover from, or more successfully adapt to actual or potential adverse events.</i>	World Road Association (PIARC, 2019)
<i>The ability of an individual, a community or a country to cope with, adapt and recover quickly from the impact of a disaster, violence or conflict. Resilience covers all stages of disaster, from prevention (when possible) to adaptation (when necessary), and includes positive transformation that strengthens the ability of current and future generations to meet their needs and withstand crises.</i>	International Organization (DG-ECHO, 2021)

A few observations may be inferred from **Table 1**, notably:

- One may wonder whether ‘resilience’ is an intrinsic (or not) property, a process, an ability, an outcome, or maybe a combination of all of these.
- The definition for ‘resilience’ has evolved over the years even within the same organization (e.g. PIARC; UNDRR, formerly UNISDR).
- Early definitions of resilience emphasize the **robustness, recovery and bounce-back** ability of the system. These represent the more “classical” view of resilience **used primarily in engineering systems** which assumes a pre-defined state of equilibrium.
- Later definitions of resilience, especially those arising from sources that involve a strong social component, emphasize the ability of the system to **transform and adapt** to a new state of equilibrium, which is closer to what is more consistent of the notion of “**ecological resilience**” (Walker & Salt., 2006).

It is needless to provide definitions for ‘community’ as these encompass every possible configuration ranging from geographical location or scale to all kinds of social networks. Nevertheless one should precisely define what they mean when using the term ‘community’ because the definition may greatly influence the way we may follow in attempting to measure and/or enhancing its ‘resilience’. The essence is that ‘resilience’ *looks notably different when linked to different conceptualizations of community* (Räsänen, Lein, Bird, & Setten, 2020). Consequently, definitions for ‘**community resilience**’ greatly vary as well. As observed in (Patel, Rogers, Amlôt, & Rubin., 2017), ‘community resilience’ can either be seen as an ongoing process of adaptation, the simple absence of negative effects, the presence of a range of positive attributes, or a mixture of all three. To conclude, one should clearly define when referring to ‘resilience’, for whom, why, when, and where (WHO, 2017).

3. Proposed approach: methodology and methods

3.1 What do we need to agree upon?

The question asked in the title of this article is purely rhetorical. It is clear and obvious that teams and projects need to have a common understanding on what ‘resilience’ is and how it is defined. The key is on which characteristics we should base such common understanding and agreement. The proposed way to proceed is to focus on which are the desired fundamental capabilities of the envisioned ‘resilient’ system. This by itself is no trivial endeavor. By looking at representative different conceptualizations of fundamental capabilities of a ‘resilient’ system, as presented in Table 2, one may infer why.

Table 2: Fundamental capabilities of a ‘resilient’ system

Fundamental capabilities of a ‘resilient’ system	Source
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Absorptive • Adaptive • Restorative 	(Vugrin, et al., 2010)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anticipatory • Absorptive • Adaptive • (Transformative) → (WHO, 2017) 	(Holling, 1993)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anticipate → what to expect • Respond → what to do • Monitor → What to look for • Learn → What happened 	(Hollnagel, 2011)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan/Prepare • Absorb • Recover 	(U.S. National Academy of Sciences, 2012)

- *Adapt*
 - *Be prepared* → *avoid*
 - *Be flexible* → *survive*
 - *Be adaptable* → *recover*
- (Hollnagel & Woods, Epilogue: Resilience engineering precepts, 2006)
-

Table 2, provides different notions for the fundamental capabilities of a ‘resilient’ system that may exist in the scientific community. Even when using the same terms, depending on the context or definition, these may imply a different concept when used by a different source.

When dealing with systems that include strong social components, (Kruse, et al., 2017) argue that *‘Limiting resilience to narrow interpretations of robust infrastructure (bounce-back to pre-determined state concept) would promote local disaster risk reduction that fails to address the need for social change and learning’*.

The aforementioned highlight the imperative need to establish a common understanding and agreement among involved stakeholders when addressing ‘resilience’ of transportation systems. For systems involving a strong ‘social’ dimension such as the case is in various transport systems, one should keep in mind that there is *no evidence of a common agreed definition of ‘community resilience’* and thus, as aforementioned, the way we define it will unavoidably affect the way we will attempt to measure and enhance it (Cutter, 2016). Therefore, naturally, the next question arises.

3.2 How to establish a common understanding and agreement?

In evidence of the complex and sometimes confusing landscape on the variety of definitions for ‘resilience’ and ‘community resilience’ (Cutter, 2016) argues that *‘it may be easier, clearer and more useful for academics, policy-makers and responders to be explicit as to the particular elements of resilience they are focusing on in their research or interventions’*.

The aforementioned suggestion forms the core element of our proposed approach. Another essential element of the proposed approach is its strong participatory element which forms the ground both for establishing and sharing a common background and understanding on the possible use of the various terms, a necessary precondition for an informed agreement on the use of these terms. **Figure 1** provides an overview of the proposed approach by summarizing the aim of each step and providing relevant methods (non-exhaustive list) that may be applied to each step. The major steps are next briefly analyzed.

I. Scope & context: This is an important step which will set the course and direction for the overall exercise. Clearly setting the scope and relevant context for the system to be studied / analyzed by involving key stakeholders will provide the variety of perspectives and opinions that need to be taken into account and synthesized into a common understanding of the envisioned endeavor. Different (mis-)conceptions and perspectives should be presented and discussed so that all parties become aware and familiar with these. Expert/stakeholder consultations in common meeting is the proposed participatory method that could be greatly facilitated from some preliminary background desktop search on the specific topic.

II. Identify: Having set a clear scope and relevant context, the next step should constitute of identifying fundamental ‘resilience’ or ‘community resilience’ elements in the form of attributes and/or capacities that would be most applicable to the pre-defined scope and context. In this context, agreeing on the fundamental set of resources to promote resiliency attributes/capacities and support decision-making is an important precondition for further advancing and deepening the scope and context of the analysis. A top-bottom critical and comparative analysis performed by subject matter experts that is based on literature review (top-down) and case study collection (bottom-up) approaches is proposed as the method to follow. Top-down approach may provide the ability to compare across different scales and units of analysis (e.g. local, national, international) using standardized data. On the other hand, bottom-up approaches may provide the necessary detail and knowledge/information at local scale which could be used for refining generic findings to the relevant context. In case, ‘community resilience’ is addressed, ‘community’ must be clearly defined.

Figure 1: Methodological approach and proposed methods

III. Refine & survey: The most challenging step is this one. Key stakeholder and/or ‘community’ needs (thereafter named ‘user needs’) in relation to the scoping and context must be determined in the form of criteria and/or indicators (e.g. KPIs). The challenging part rests in combining these key user needs with the ‘resilience’ or ‘community resilience’ attributes/capacities in order to identify relevant gaps and derive suitable recommendations. User surveys/interviews and focus group discussions where these findings (also arising from

Step II) may be integrated and synthesized into useful insight for structuring a GAP analysis are the proposed methods. The overarching aim is to structure the GAP analysis in a way and format that will facilitate to the best of its ability the collection of specific and context-based gaps so that specific recommendations may be derived in Step IV. The proposed GAP structure and/or findings may be further validated in stakeholder meetings/workshops.

IV. Analyze & finalize: The final step consists of administering the GAP survey to the stakeholders/‘community’ of interest and analyzing the collected feedback with the aim, as aforementioned to provide as specific and practical as possible, recommendations for the development of proposed technologies and system operationalization that will be relevant the enhancement of the ‘resilience’ or of the ‘community resilience’ as defined. Clearly, the aim here is to avoid to the possible extent generalities that may be applicable under any case and circumstances by focusing on the specific context. It is in this sense, that a final workshop including the participation of external to the project/consortium experts as well is advised for a final refinement and possible validation of the survey findings and recommendations.

4. Discussion: preliminary findings and suggestions for further research

It may be useful to remind the reader at this point that our proposed approach does not aim at its current state to propose a measure for the ‘resilience’ or the ‘community resilience’ of the studied system. Rather, the aim is to establish the important links between the relevant ‘resilience’ or ‘community resilience’ features with the end-user needs as commonly understood and agreed among the different stakeholders so as to best guide the development of technology and its operationalization in relation to those ‘resilience’ features. In this sense, it provides a high-level direction to the intended scope.

How to measure the resulting ‘resilience’ or ‘community resilience’ is an entire area of research with several proposed qualitative and quantitative methodologies that may rely on qualitative attributes of the system, key performance indicators (KPIs) on aspects of ‘resilience’ and/or an aggregate single indicator for ‘resilience’. This is out of the scope of our study.

The proposed approach is currently being applied in the Horizon 2020 EU-funded Research and Innovation (RIA) project S&R and based on the acquired experience preliminary findings on the advantages and shortcomings or areas of potential research are presented in *Table 3*. The interested reader may refer to the deliverables of the project, once publicly available, for a detailed description of the implementation of the proposed approach.

Table 3: Advantages and potential improvements of the proposed approach

Major advantages	Drawbacks / areas for potential improvement
A stakeholder-oriented participatory approach that breaks ‘silo’- thinking.	Time-expensive approach requiring expert commitment.
Actively engages stakeholders/end-users in the formulation of a common understanding of	In its current state, it does not allow for an ‘easy’ quantitative estimate of the ‘resilience’ or

essential principles and concepts.

‘community resilience’ features
it aims at considering.

Easily adaptable under different context and
audience. This potential also extends to the use of
different participatory methods for consensus-
building (e.g. Delphi, Nominal Group Technique).

Requires experience in
moderating stakeholder / focus
group meetings and good prior
preparation for these.

Allows integration of quantitative methods (e.g.
multi-criteria analysis, vulnerability, risk analysis).
Creative thinking is also encouraged.

Facilitates and enhances positive communication
between concerned stakeholders and parties.

Established based on widely accepted research and
participatory methods, an aspect that is particularly
positively valued when considering the
‘community’/social component.

Top-down, bottom-up approach.

As listed in **Table 3** there are several advantages to the proposed approach and these have been confirmed at the relevant S&R Workshop of Step IV with the participation of 300+ experts, both internal and external to the S&R consortium. However, the proposed approach also leaves room and provides food for thought for further research and improvements. The major advancement of this approach in our opinion would be to systematically and practically integrate it in the assessment of the ‘resilience’ or ‘community resilience’ of the system once additional consensus or unanimity on this topic is (if needed and ever) made possible by the scientific community. Until then, it is up to individual ‘resilience’ assessment frameworks to constructively integrate it within.

We should also observe that the proposed participatory methods are indicative and could be substituted in some cases by other methods (e.g. Delphi, stakeholder analysis, Nominal Group Technique).

5. Conclusions

An approach based on participatory methods has been proposed for guiding the establishment of common stakeholder perceptions, facilitating and enhancing communication related to the ‘resilience’ and ‘community resilience’ concepts.

The vagueness, variety and different conceptualizations that exist in the scientific literature in relation to the aforementioned concepts inspired this approach. As ‘resilience’ is increasingly called for by various stakeholders in every possible context, the authors believe that it is indispensable to create and achieve a solid contextual understanding that is shared among involved stakeholders and ‘communities’.

Several advantages of the proposed approach have been presented. Its participative nature, and its potential for adaptability in different contexts and settings constitute its primary and

most prominent characteristics. The transportation sector consisting of several stakeholders that often include an important ‘community’ or social dimension is appealing for the application of the proposed approach. In particular, when used for guiding the development and/or operationalization of transportation technologies / infrastructures. Furthermore, the proposed approach has been implemented in the context of the RIA Horizon 2020 EU-funded project S&R and a dedicated Workshop with 300+ experts (both internal and external to the Consortium) participating was used for its proposed refinement and validation.

Nevertheless, the proposed approach does not, at least at this stage of maturity, substitute for the need to provide or establish specific quantitative measures of ‘resilience’ or ‘community resilience’ which is a topic of ongoing creativity and debate in the scientific community. In this respect, and based on the acquired experience, the study offers possible directions for further research in relation to the proposed approach.

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